

THE EFFECTS OF TEST RATE ON THE FRACTURE BEHAVIOUR OF ADHESIVELY BONDED JOINTS

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SUMMARY

The present work investigates the effects of test rate on the fracture behaviour of adhesively bonded joints. A fracture mechanics methodology has been developed to accurately measure the mode I fracture resistance over a wide range of test rates. Double cantilever beam (DCB) and tapered double cantilever beam (TDCB) tests were performed and the results were interpreted using a newly developed analysis strategy.

Keywords: Adhesive joint, fracture mechanics, high rate, dynamic effects, international standard.

Introduction

The use of structural adhesives to bond polymer composites and light weight alloys is now well established within the aerospace and automotive industries. The characterisation of adhesive joints using a fracture mechanics approach is also well established for mode I (the tensile opening mode) at slow rates [1, 2]. These now internationally agreed standards employ the double cantilever beam (DCB) and the tapered double cantilever beam (TDCB) test specimens as shown in Figure 1. These comprise fibre-composite or metallic substrates adhesively bonded together using a structural adhesive. A starter crack is formed by placing a thin release film centrally in the adhesive layer during manufacture and a natural crack is formed using a pre-cracking procedure described in [1, 2]. The resistance to both the initiation of this natural crack and its subsequent propagation is determined using corrected beam theory approaches. The resistance to fracture is characterised using the fracture energy, G_{IC} .

Increasingly, there is a need to characterise the performance of adhesively bonded joints at higher test rates [3, 4]. This stems from the increased use of adhesives in automotive structural applications which may be subject to road shocks and impact damage during vehicle collision. During such a crash event the role of the adhesive, which may be used (i) to bond composite parts, (ii) to bond parts of an alloy space frame or indeed, (iii) to bond parts of the energy absorbing crumple structure, will be crucial. It is important that the adhesive does not fail in a brittle manner, but is able to transmit the loads across the joint such that the deformation mechanisms in the substrates can take place during the impact. The vast majority of the crash energy may then be absorbed via plastic deformation of metallic structures or by the multiple damage mechanisms which occur in fibre-composite crush tube structures [5].

In the present work, a detailed investigation into the fracture behaviour of structural adhesive joints using the DCB and TDCB test specimens at test rates of up to 15m/s is described. A number of different substrate materials of use in the automotive industry have been investigated. The objective has been to establish a robust experimental procedure and associated analysis strategy. It is also intended that such work will prepare the ground for a future high rate test standard for structural adhesive joints. In addition, the utility of a thermal model has been explored as the likely explanation for the variations in fracture resistance deduced.

Experimental

Two types of fracture mechanics test specimen employing three different substrate materials have been studied in the present work. The substrates have been adhesively bonded using a toughened automotive grade adhesive. The adhesive used was a rubber-toughened single-part epoxy: Betamate XD4600 from Dow Automotive. This is a structural automotive-grade adhesive, specially developed to resist sudden loading and to accommodate various types of substrates including slightly oily metals as typically found in industrial applications. The substrates used to manufacture the TDCB joints investigated were aluminium alloy EN AW-2014 [6]. This alloy is used in high strength structural components. Two unidirectionally reinforced carbon-fibre composite substrates were also investigated. The composite HTS/6376 was supplied by Hexcel Composites and IM7/977-2 was supplied by Cytec Engineered Materials. DCB specimens were formed with the composite substrates and TDCB specimens were formed with the aluminium alloy substrates, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. (a) The double cantilever beam (DCB) specimen and (b) the tapered double cantilever beam (TDCB) adhesive joint test specimen indicating loading and length, x_0 (see Table 2).

The joints were tested in mode I under quasi-static and at high loading rates of up to 15m/s. A test rig was developed using a high-speed servo-hydraulic test machine and incorporated a high speed video camera to record the beam displacements, the crack length and crack velocity histories as a function of time. The test rig is shown schematically in Figure 2, depicting the set up for a DCB test.

Figure 2. Schematic figure of the high rate test set up and data acquisition.

A procedure was developed to determine the relevant test parameters from the high speed video traces. A high speed data acquisition system collected all the input data and synchronised the various data channels. This procedure is described fully in [7-8].

Interpretation of crack growth

Four distinct regions of crack growth behaviour were identified from the tests. At the slowest test rates, crack propagation was stable and continuous. Also, at the slowest speeds, the effects of kinetic energy were negligible and this fracture type was termed Type 1. At faster test rates, there was a transition to unstable, stick-slip crack propagation. However, at the lower test rates, the effects of kinetic energy were still small and this fracture type was termed Type 2. At faster test rates, the effects of kinetic energy became increasingly significant. When these effects reached 5% of the measured value of the fracture energy, then they were taken into account in the analysis. This fracture type was termed Type 3. Finally, as the rate of loading was increased further, the crack growth behaviour appeared to revert to continuous growth and this has been termed, Type 4. These crack propagation types are summarised in Table 1.

Table 1. Crack propagation behaviour and analysis type

Fracture type	1	2	3	4
Behaviour	Stable	Stick-slip	Stick-slip	Stable [†]
k.e. significant?	No	No	Yes	Yes
Load reliable?	Yes	Yes	No	No

[†] Apparently continuous

Analysis

An analysis was developed for each of the four distinct types of crack propagation defined; namely Type 1: slow-stable; Type 2: slow-stick slip; Type 3 fast-stick-slip and Type 4 fast stable. A protocol was developed to analyse these fracture types accurately and reproducibly [7-8]. For the DCB and TDCB tests, the mode I fracture energy, G_{IC} was determined using a load-independent dynamic analysis, corrected for the effects of kinetic energy in the different specimens. Beam theory expressions developed previously have been modified to i) make them load independent and ii) to correct the values of G_{IC} for effects of kinetic energy. The use of the load-independent dynamic analysis has been previous reported for the high rate DCB analysis [9], but the main equations are summarised in Table 2.

Table 2. Analysis for the DCB test specimen

Analysis Type	Analysis Equations (Experimental data used)
Type 1	$G_{Ic} = \frac{3 P \delta}{2 b (a + \Delta_I)} \cdot \frac{F}{N}$ ([†])
Type 2	$G_{Ic} = \frac{3 P \delta}{2 b (a + \Delta_I)} \cdot \frac{F}{N}$ ([§])
Type 3	$G_{Ic} = \frac{3 E h^3 (V/2)^2 t^2}{4 (a + \Delta_I)^4} \frac{F}{N^2} - \frac{33 E h (V/2)^2}{140 c_L^2}$ ([§])
Type 4	$G_{Ic} = \frac{3 E h^3 (V/2)^2 t^2}{4 (a + \Delta_I)^4} \frac{F}{N^2} - \frac{111 E h (V/2)^2}{280 c_L^2}$ ([†])

([†]) Crack propagation values used; ([§]) crack initiation values used.

Where P is the load, δ the beam opening displacement, a the crack length, b the joint width, F , N and Δ_I are correction factors described in [1], V is the test velocity, t the test time, E the

longitudinal modulus of the substrate, h the height of the substrate and c_L the longitudinal wave speed.

For the TDCB specimen, a dynamic analysis proposed in [10] has been modified to account additionally for the straight portion of the TDCB profile, x_0 , as shown in Figure 1, and to incorporate the crack length correction for beam root rotation effects as proposed by Blackman et al. [11]. The full derivation of the dynamic analysis for the TDCB test specimen may be found in [8], but the main equations are summarised in Table 3.

Table 3. Analysis for the TDCB test specimen

Analysis Type	Analysis Equations (Experimental data used)
Type 1	$G_{ic} = \frac{4P^2 m}{Eb^2} \left[1 + 0.43 \left(\frac{3}{ma} \right)^{1/3} \right] \quad (\dagger)$
Type 2	$G_{ic} = \frac{4P^2 m}{Eb^2} \left[1 + 0.43 \left(\frac{3}{ma} \right)^{1/3} \right] \quad (\S)$
Type 3	$G_{ic} = \frac{E}{4m} \left[\frac{\delta}{2a^*} \right]^2 \left[1 + 0.43 \left(\frac{3}{ma} \right)^{1/3} \right] \left[1 - 3 \left(\frac{9}{22} \right)^3 \left(\frac{a^*}{c_L t} \right)^2 m \cdot h(a^*) \right] \quad (\S)$
Type 4	$G_{ic} = G_{ic}^s \left\{ 1 - \frac{9}{11} \left(\frac{\dot{a}}{c_L} \right)^2 \left[1 + 0.43 \left(\frac{3}{ma} \right)^{1/3} \right]^2 m \cdot h(a^*) \right\}$ where $G_{ic}^s = \frac{E}{4m} \left[\frac{(V/2)}{\dot{a}} \right]^2 \left[1 + 0.43 \left(\frac{3}{ma} \right)^{1/3} \right]^{-1} \quad (\dagger)$

(\dagger) Crack propagation values used; (\S) crack initiation values used.

where the terms have the same meaning as above with the addition of m being the geometry factor for the TDCB specimen: $m = \left(\frac{3a^2}{h^3} + \frac{1}{h} \right)$, a^* crack length measured from $a = (2/3) \times x_0$, $h(a^*)$ is the height of the substrate at a^* , and \dot{a} is the crack velocity.

Results & Discussion

The experimental parameters recorded were used to determine the values of the fracture energy, G_{IC} , as a function of test velocity for either crack initiation or crack propagation, according to the protocol outlined above. Crack propagation remained essentially cohesive in the adhesive layer for these joints. Figure 3 shows the values of G_{IC} calculated as a function of test loading rate. The regions where the different fracture types were observed are shown on Figure 3.

Figure 3. Values of G_{IC} versus test rate for the TDCB (▲) DCB (●) joints bonded with the tough automotive adhesive as a function of test rate.

Additionally, the presentation will describe the dependence of G_{IC} upon measured crack velocity and upon various time parameters used to describe the adiabatic heating effects which are known to occur at the tip of a rapidly moving crack in various polymers. The use of an isothermal-adiabatic model to describe the reduction in adhesive fracture energy with increasing test rate is explored. It is noteworthy that the time dependence of the value of G_{IC} may be shown to be a function of the timescale of the test via a dependency which is most conveniently plotted as G_{IC} versus the time of loading in the form of $t_i^{-1/2}$, where t_i is the time required to initiate the crack. It is shown that this parameter is the most appropriate parameter to use as opposed to using the rate of test or the crack velocity, which is clearly dependent upon the geometry and stiffness of the joint tested. Such considerations have been described in detail recently in [12].

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